

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

A Textbook Model in a Foreign Language for Specific Purposes: Tourism Sphere

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Abstract

The article deals with the recent problem of teaching a foreign language to specialists in the sphere of service and production. The demand for personnel with a professional linguistic competence has remained high on the labor market over the past decade. The teaching community is actively developing new training courses and programs in the foreign language of the specialty, an important component of which is mastering the language of the professional sphere. However, the question of creating textbooks for narrow-focused specialists (air traffic controllers, pilots, navigators, medical personnel, tourism workers) remains open, for such specialists a foreign language is a tool that allows them to carry out their professional activities. The article clarifies the content of the terms "language of specialty" and "language for specific purposes", which is reflected in the organization of courses in the language of specialty and technology of courses in language for specific purposes. The results of the experimental training have showed the effectiveness of the program "French in the field of tourism" and revealed the need to write a textbook. The author's proposed model of the textbook "French in the field of tourism" is intended for students of language universities, faculties of tourism, staff of hotels and travel agencies and includes the following components: modularity of the course, special vocabulary, a list of professional skills and communicative situations of business communication, methodological techniques that allow to form readiness for professional activity. This tutorial model can be extrapolated to other languages and training profile.

Keywords: foreign language for specific purposes, linguistic professional competence.

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Introduction

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Language for Specific Purposes. The French concept of teaching a language for specific purposes (*Langues sur objectifs spécifiques - LOS*), which arose during the same period, was based on the work of Hutchinson and Waters on teaching English for Specific Purposes. The main problematics of FOS was developed for specialists and students of non-linguistic faculties who want to master the French language in their professional field and realize specific goals and objectives, hence the name - "*objectifs spécifiques*" (specific goals).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of professional training of students under the program "French in the field of tourism" is the formation of linguistic professional competence, where the professional component involves the mastery of the future specialist with the whole range of knowledge, skills and abilities characteristic of the personnel in the tourism industry. The linguistic component of the formed competence is implemented in various types of speech activity, which presupposes a high level of perception and generation of speech utterances, interactive actions for solving professional problems. For the formation of linguistic professional competence, we use such techniques as role-playing game, business game, simulation, project method.

Many years of experience in training personnel for the tourism sector have proved the high effectiveness of the use of the competence-based approach in teaching French for specific purposes (Cherkashina, 2019). The results of the experiment have showed the effectiveness of the modular course "French in the field of tourism": 100% of students pass for an international diploma of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Paris, demonstrating a high level of proficiency in linguistic and professional competence in the field of tourism.

Literature review

A review of publications giving an idea of the development of methodology in the field of theory and practice of teaching a foreign (French) language for specific purposes (FSP) showed the existence of varieties of language learning, depending on the needs of students (Mangiante, 2004; Mourlhon-Dallies, 2017; Delagneau, 2017). FSP covers almost all of the most requested areas:

- Le français des affaires,
- Le français de l'hôtellerie et du tourisme,
- Le français scientifique et technique,

- Le français juridique,
- Le français des relations internationales,
- Le français de la médecine,
- Le français des relations publiques et de l'administration,
- Le français du secrétariat,
- Le français des sciences sociales et humaines,
- Le français de l'informatique,
- Le français journalistique,
- Le français des transports,
- Le français des postes et télécommunications,
- Le français de traduction ou d'interprétation

Obviously, the structure of languages for specific purposes is broad and varied. It should be noted that in the practice of teaching a foreign language for specialists, there are two main approaches to teaching based on the content of the language: a broad gauged approach and a narrow gauged approach. The first one is most often used for teaching a foreign language to students starting their studies at a university. In this case, the training of a general professional (a physicist, a mathematician, an engineer, an architect) will "rely on a broad professional knowledge base, which ensures high adaptability to a specific type of professional activity and allows the specialist in a short time "deepen" the integration of linguistic professional competence with a specific narrow professional competence" (Uvarova, 2011).

The narrow gauged approach is used to teach a foreign language to air traffic controllers, pilots, navigators, people from the medical sphere, hotel personnel (Cherkashina, 2016). The process of foreign language teaching to such a specialist will be detailed at the level of professional terminology (language for specific purposes), since their professional activities can be detailed down to typical, well-defined production tasks performed in a foreign language. We are talking about deep integration of the foreign language speech component into the structure of their narrow professional competence.

The idea of the existence of these approaches finds its confirmation in the works of the famous French methodologists / didactists Zh-M. Mangiante and S. Parpet, who specialize in teaching language for specific purposes to the widest range of specialists (Mangiante et al., 2004; Mangiante, 2019). Scientists point to the existing difference between two terms: the language of the specialty (le français de spécialité) and the language for special purposes (le FOS), where the language of the specialty is taught to the general public and focuses on the discipline or the professional sphere in general. Language for specific purposes presupposes the training of narrow focused specialists and “is characterized by the technology of developing a foreign language course in each individual case” (Mangiante, 2004). A language for specific purposes is determined by the demand of those, for whom a foreign language is not a specialty, for them, first of all, it is a necessary tool for carrying out professional activities.

The basic concepts (or basic principles) of a language for specific purposes are considered to be authenticity, scientific basis, language (linguistic means), the need and methodology of the process of teaching a language for specific purposes. Let us narrow down the stated theoretical provisions in relation to a specific educational context - teaching French in the field of tourism in the system of training personnel for the tourism industry in Moscow and the Moscow region.

Methodology

In pedagogical methodology, methods are used that are applied at the empirical level: analysis of scientific and methodological literature, scientific observation, generalization of experience, questionnaires, testing. Methods used at the theoretical level are: abstraction, analysis and synthesis, comparison, modeling, extrapolation. Methods at the empirical and theoretical levels are in close interaction, since the empirical and theoretical levels of knowledge are inseparable. The generalized assessment criterion is the criteria for training and education, formation and development. The research used authentic sources (Mangiante, 2017; Mourlhon-Dallies, 2017; Tareva, 2018).

Results

A model of the textbook "French in the field of tourism". Today, more than ever, the question of the actual use of new models in teaching and the creation of specialized educational resources that meet the modern didactic and methodological requirements is acute. The model of the textbook proposed by us is intended for teaching the French language of tourism to students of specialized universities, as well as personnel of hotels and travel agencies, and includes the following components: course modularity, special vocabulary, including terms and professionalisms, a list of professional skills and communicative situations of

professional communication, methodological techniques that allow the formation of linguo-professional competence within the framework of a quasi professional activity.

Figure: 1 Model of the textbook "French in the field of tourism"

This model of the textbook "French in the field of tourism" is focused on specialization in three sectors: hotel and restaurant business, tourism as an industry / service sector, where great importance is attached to the realities of industrial, organizational and managerial culture (Cherkashina, 2017). The emphasis is on the formation of appropriate psychological attitudes of service personnel in accordance with the requirements of European standards of service. The declared modules: Hôtellerie, Restauration, Tourisme, are relevant to the tourism industry and include basic concepts (professional concepts) to be studied. It is the understanding of the basic concepts of each module, their integrated unity in the minds of students that will be a condition for the successful performance of professional duties and inclusion in the structure of the tourism business.

The content of the tutorial clearly states the goals of teaching French in the sphere of tourism (see Figure

1):

- professional goals (to inform the client, develop programs for the stay of tourists in the country, offer travel routes and organize them, compose brochures, booklets, sell a tourist product);
- communicative goals (to be able to understand the requests, wishes, requirements, complaints of the client; to request information, to be able to explain, describe, offer services);
- sociocultural goals (the ability to organize communication taking into account the rules, norms and traditions of verbal and non-verbal behavior in the country of the target language);
- linguistic goals (proper linguistic knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, phonetics).

Within each module, as a sphere of professional communication, it is necessary to form the skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of specific goals: in the hotel - be able to receive / place a client, book a room, negotiate by phone; in a restaurant - be able to accept an order, explain the menu, advise / offer dishes to customers, advertise your products; in a travel agency - to understand client's requests, inform about travel, offer a tourist product, advise, argue, bargain, etc. Formation and development of these skills and abilities is the priority task of teaching French for specific purposes in tourism sphere.

Based on experience of the famous French linguodidact Jean-Marc Mangiante in developing training programs "Language for specific purposes" for archaeologists, agronomists, ophthalmologists, which are effectively implemented in the training of narrow focused specialists in Europe (Mangiante 2004), we offer the following structure of the textbook:

1. Rationale for the course: students' needs analysis, the request of employers.
2. Course content.
3. Schedule, number of hours per week.
4. The contingent of students, training profile, specialty.
5. The needs of students: oral and written communication, level of foreign language proficiency.
6. Entrance test for the level of proficiency in a foreign language.
7. Working program of the course.

8. Purpose, tasks of professional and verbal communication.
9. Authentic course materials: professional publications, catalogs, brochures, websites.
10. Modular exam.

Let's look at the structure and content of the first module of the textbook "Hôtellerie" (hotel service). The study of the field of hospitality and accommodation of tourists in hotels is a paramount task in the tourism industry, as the first rule says - first to accommodate a tourist for the night and provide him with comfort. The second task is to feed the tourist, and only the third task is to organize leisure activities for the tourist, offer him excursions and entertainment. Therefore, the Hôtellerie module (hotel service) opens the first stage of travel organization to students, shows the importance of comfortable rest and sleep for clients, and also provides with the knowledge necessary in the third module "Tourisme" when it comes to developing travel itineraries, tours, excursion programs, visits. Note that the module "Tourisme" accumulates the knowledge and professional skills acquired within the previously studied modules "Hôtellerie" and "Restauration".

Module "Hôtellerie" includes the following thematic sections:

1. Welcome to the hotel!
2. European category of hotels (criteria, European standards, service).
3. Describe the hotel (location, building type, restaurant / bar availability, transport accessibility, etc.).
4. Offer the rooms (number of rooms, comfort, view from the window, the presence of a balcony / loggia, a safe, a minibar, etc.).
5. Meet the client / group at the reception (check the reservation, familiarize with the rules of stay, fill in the client's dossier, give the key).
6. Book rooms by phone and the internet.
7. Confirm your room reservation. Cancel / change booking by email.
8. Inform the client about services, transport, attractions.
9. Accept an order for calling a taxi, ordering a table in a restaurant, booking tickets to the theater and

excursions.

10. Respond to customer complaints, solve problems.

Each thematic section begins with the study of special vocabulary and a thematic vocabulary, or rather, with language structures, syntactic models as the basis of professional communication. In our opinion, traditional memorization of vocabulary with a list is ineffective, therefore we offer students a list of phrases / models of professional communication for each stage of working with a client, starting with a greeting at the reception. The specified order of studying language models reflects the stages of work with a client, the rules for registering / settling a client in a hotel, the order of performing their duties. While studying speech patterns the professional skill of working at the reception is mastered. The automated skill of working with a client allows one to comply with the requirements of professional communication: literary style and obligatory formulas of courtesy.

Within each section of the module "Hôtellerie", techniques such as role-playing, business games, and simulation are used. These socially oriented techniques are aimed at interaction, interactive communication in pairs, and groups of students. Achievement of the required level of linguistic professional competence is possible through the use of situationally conditioned language teaching with the help of communication-oriented exercises, which include role-playing games. Role play as a form of imitation modeling of the conditions for future professional activity allows the game participants to develop and improve professionally oriented skills.

In our manual, we offer communication exercises / role-play games for typical situations in a hotel (client - hotel staff), which require a quick response, professional competence, verbal skills of conditionally unprepared speech:

1. You work at the reception, a client arrives at the hotel who has not booked a room, he is passing through the city for one night. You have room stock and can accommodate a client.
2. You work at the reception, a client arrives at the hotel who has not booked a room, he is passing through the city for one night. All rooms in the hotel are occupied / booked, you are sorry that you cannot accommodate a client. Offer him a list of hotels of the same category, located in the same area.
3. You work at the reception, a group of tourists arrives at the hotel who need more rooms than has been booked. You offer different rooms and find an opportunity to accommodate additional 3 people.

In the tasks for role-play games, the vitality, typicality and concreteness of situations are traced, as well as

the regularity in the repetition of tasks and procedures. However, in real life, hotel staff have to solve non-standard, often conflict situations, and business games help here - as a method of imitating decision-making by managers or specialists in an interactive mode, in the presence of conflict situations or information uncertainty. The business game allows us to radically reduce the time for accumulating professional experience, gives us the opportunity to experiment with an event, try different strategies for solving the problems posed, and form a holistic view of professional activity in its dynamics in future specialists. Participation in business games is a quasi-professional activity of students which allows them to form professional skills and develop in the process of this activity the ability and willingness to solve problematic tasks that arise in the workplace. Quasi-professional activity in the organization of business games allows us to stimulate students to spontaneous role-based communication in a foreign language in the field of professional activity.

In the process of conducting business games, the emphasis is placed on the psychological aspect of acquiring linguistic professional competence. When students try on certain roles in the field of professional activity, they learn the models of behavior of residents of the country of the target language, develop professional skills for working with a foreign client. At the same time, there is an improvement in all language skills: the correctness of the construction of syntactic structures, the correct choice of grammatical forms, the automatism in the use of formulas of politeness in accordance with the rules and norms of verbal communication of the country of the target language.

Each situation in the module is implemented in all types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, writing), the emphasis is on the formation of professional skills in a foreign language. When writing business letters (hotel booking request, booking confirmation / cancellation, complaint, invoice, booklet, advertising insert), one must follow the business correspondence requirements. When listening - to understand the client's request, understand and write down the necessary information to work with the client. Test tasks and the main types of exercises in the studied module are aimed at the formation and development of verbal communication skills. Along with various types of exercises, students are given extensive socio-cultural information about the country. First of all, these are the realities of production, organizational and managerial culture, familiarity with existing cultural traditions.

Simulation (simulation globale), as a technique, allows to create your own hotel, give it a name, select a category, clientele, staff within the framework of one module, for example, the hotel industry, and at each subsequent stage use this distribution of roles, this situational shell to achieve private goals. For instance, describe the hotel (a new thematic vocabulary is being trained), make cards for each client (fiche cardex) with descriptions of habits, requirements, features, assign roles and functional responsibilities for staff. In

this case, the entire group is involved and everyone can choose a role for themselves at the moment of training, both linguistically and professionally. This technique enables each student to participate in the educational process, and not passively attend classes. We bear in mind that simulation as a business game is a rather laborious and resource-intensive form of training; the result obtained may not always justify the funds spent on organizing this educational process.

The use of authentic materials in language learning for special purposes is mandatory, since they recreate real situations and problems of professional activity in the context of practical training (Mangiante, 2019). In this textbook, we offer a list of electronic resources: websites of hotels, tourism offices, regions of France, electronic catalogs of the world's leading tour operators, electronic guides, brochures. Information about hotels and services, their prices should be up-to-date and reflect the trends and requests of tourists. Within the framework of the module, not only the infrastructure of the hotel business is studied, but also rural housing (cottages, farms, country houses, hunting lodges, sports facilities), which has become very popular in Europe due to the development of rural tourism since the beginning of the 21st century.

Training in each area of tourism ends with a modular exam in all types of speech activity:

- listening (compréhension orale): understanding client requests, booking a room by phone, confirming a booking, filling in order forms after listening;
- comprehension of written text (compréhension écrite): tests to check professional knowledge of hotel categories, service and comfort, personnel requirements, as well as linguistic knowledge and knowledge of a thematic vocabulary;
- writing business letters (production écrite): confirm the booking request / cancel the booking, write the text of the hotel booklet (depliant);
- oral communication (production orale): participation in a role-play game, work with a client in a given situation.

The given structure of the textbook can be traced in the content of each module, only the thematic vocabulary and the employee's functionality (taches professionnelles) change. The enrichment of linguistic knowledge, an increase in vocabulary, the formation of unprepared speech skills occurs in a "spiral", the studied language means of the first modules are actively used in the speech practice of the third module "Tourisme".

Despite the widespread use of authentic materials: guides, catalogs, travel brochures, guidebooks, booklets,

brochures, advertising inserts, as well as websites of hotels, tour operators, regions of France, students need a teaching aid for the proposed course. A textbook will systematically present the goals and objectives of the course, the content of the modules, the professional tasks of mastering each section, the specifics of language exercises / tests for special purposes, requirements for tasks, training tests for the unit exam.

Discussions

The question of the structure and content of a textbook on language for specific purposes remains debatable. Foreign authors actively use the modular structure of the course, which should be reflected in the manual (Tareva, 2020). However, the content of the modules is focused on familiarization with the sectors and types of tourism, the list of professions and partners. Formation of the professional skills and abilities such as work with a client in a hotel, restaurant, travel agency; creation of a tourist product, sale and advertising of services is given fragmentarily in each module (Corbeau et al., 2014). In our opinion, it is rather difficult to form professional skills, for example, working with a client, simultaneously in the three specified areas. Communication situations in a hotel and in a travel agency are fundamentally different. Working with a client in a hotel requires knowledge of speech patterns, which, in turn, reflect the functionality and responsibilities of an employee at the reception. Accordingly, we observe the difference in linguistic structures and syntactic models for each field of tourism and each module of the textbook. This is the main difference between a textbook / study guide on the language of a specialty and a textbook on a language for specific purposes, "which is essentially a technology for developing a foreign language course in each individual case" (Mangiante, 2004). In a textbook on teaching a language for specific purposes, the process of language training of a narrow focus specialist will be detailed at the level of their professional activity, which should be detailed to typical, clearly defined production tasks performed in a foreign language.

The trend is noticed towards simplification of the language material of foreign textbooks and, accordingly, a decrease in the requirements for the level of language proficiency. Textbooks over the past five years have shown a tendency to start teaching the language of a specialty at the A1 level (Laygues et al., 2014; Dussac, 2017) and are focused on familiarization with the field of activity, on the formation of primary professional skills. However, language manuals for specific purposes, aimed at training competent personnel, declare the final level of language proficiency B1-B2 (Bencini et al., 2016).

Conclusion

The dynamically developing sphere of tourism in Russia has revealed a demand for competent specialists who have undergone special training. To solve this problem, professional training of personnel is proposed

in accordance with European requirements, namely, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Paris. The developed and tested French language courses in the tourism sector follow the main / basic principle of the language for specific purposes - the use of authentic materials: guides, catalogs, travel brochures, guidebooks, booklets, as well as websites of hotels, tour operators, regions of France. However, learners need a teaching aid for the proposed course, a textbook in which the modules, the tasks of mastering each module, the specifics of exercises / tests and the requirements for the tasks of the module will be systematically presented. Many years of experience in teaching a foreign language in the professional sphere of tourism has made it possible to develop a model of a textbook, the modular structure of which makes the study of special vocabulary in the structure of communicative situations of business communication more productive. The declared professional, communicative, sociocultural, linguistic goals are systematically realized in each module and form professional skills and readiness for professional activity (Tareva, 2017). In the author's model of the textbook, each module in a concentrated form represents professional situations, production responsibilities and the functionality of an employee in a specific production area. Following the logic of the modules of the textbook, we teach specialties through a foreign language. The main goal and purpose of the training manual on foreign language for special purposes is to prepare a specialist for the implementation of professional activities in a foreign language, the formation of linguistic professional competence. Professional training and a diploma of the Paris Chamber of Commerce and Industry allows graduates to successfully realize themselves in today's labor market.

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